

Creating the Links: Establishing Home School Learning of Mathematics through Paired Maths and Maths Eyes Initiatives

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In light of COVID-19 and the unprecedented interruption to education that came with it, the research school sought to address and ameliorate the consequences of the two-year disruption to pupil learning. The research school looked to implement and evaluate a Paired Maths and Maths Eyes initiative at a whole school level. The aim of these chosen initiatives are to empower parents to get involved in their child’s mathematics learning, improve and foster home school links in a curricular area, improve parent-child relationships, parents’ own learning, and make learning through mathematics fun. These initiatives aim to promote active learning, improve concentration and help pupils develop problem-solving skills. The activities involved in the Paired Maths initiative allow for repetition and consolidation of concepts. Attention was also given to the reinforcement of mathematical language.

Keywords: parental involvement, primary mathematics, homework

Effectiveness of Parental Involvement in Children’s Mathematics Education

Numerous researchers have sought to identify those aspects of parental involvement that are the most effective in influencing students' learning generally (Bailey, 2006) and in mathematics in particular (Cai et al, 2003). Contributing factors to children’s mathematical achievement range from parental expectation, students’ perception of parental involvement or influence (Cai et al, 2006); parents’ beliefs in their child’s competence (Aunola et al, 2003) or parental involvement in interactive homework activities (Bailey, 2006). According to Bailey (2006) increasing student learning through meaningful parent-child interaction during the completion of homework has emerged as a significant variable for improving learning outcomes of low-performing students.

Methodology

Table 1

Overview of Research Schedule

September	☐ Preparation and organisation/inventory of resources ☐ Information workshop for parents
October - December	☐ Junior class and middle class 6 week roll out ☐ Questionnaire for Parents/Pupils/Teacher Focus Group interviews with pupils ☐ Evaluate findings ☐ Feedback to staff to inform phase 2
January - March	☐ Roll out of Paired Maths in middle and senior classes for 6 weeks

- Questionnaire for Parents/Pupils/Teachers Focus Group interviews with Pupils
- Evaluate findings
- Share findings with staff and school community

March -Maths Eyes

Whole school initiative

A week in March was identified by whole staff where homework was Maths Eyes and working as Maths Detectives

- Information shared with parents explaining Maths Eyes initiative
- A mixture of qualitative and quantitative data methods were used through questionnaires and focus group interviews

Findings and Discussion

Parents welcomed the alternative approach to mathematics homework with many acknowledging that mathematics does not have to be confined to the mathematics textbook for it to have meaning and value. Questionnaires and focus group interviews found that pupils were challenged more in a meaningful way, they were engaged with the tasks, and displayed greater intrinsic motivation to learn and solve problems. The Maths Eyes allowed pupils to take on the role of Maths Detectives where they looked at the world around them through a mathematical lens. It allowed them the freedom to be creative and imaginative. Pupils challenged each other to problem solve, make meaning, ask questions, prove their solutions to their peers, be open to the different solutions of others and learn alternative methods in which problems could also be solved. Pupils were communicating using appropriate mathematical language, making connections and reasoning. Pupils also enjoyed the autonomy of being a Maths Detective.

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